

ToxTrac

2026 Version 1.4

DEV: Professor Alvaro Rodriguez (a.tajes@udc.es)

Free Animal Tracking Software

User and Technical Overview Manual

Alvaro Rodriguez^{1,2*}, Andres Molaes-Ulloa^{1,2}, Magnus Andersson³, Tomas Brodin⁴

¹ Universidade da Coruña, Dept. of Computer Science, 15071, A Coruña, Spain.

² Centro de investigación CITIC, 15071, A Coruña, Spain.

³ Umeå University, Dept. of Physics, 901 87 Umeå, Sweden.

⁴ Umeå University, Dept. of Ecology and Environmental Science, 901 87 Umeå, Sweden.

* Corresponding author: a.tajes@udc.es (Alvaro Rodriguez).

Keywords: animal behavior; ecology; tracking software

Grant PID2021-126289OA-100 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF A way of making Europe

Kempestiftelserna

IISD Experimental Lakes Area Inc

Contents

Starting Guide.....	5
1. License.....	5
2. Recommended Citations.....	5
3. Third-party components	6
4. Requirements.....	6
5. Installing and running the software	6
6. Known Issues	7
7. Recording an experiment.....	8
Video format.....	8
Resolution and framerate.....	8
Contrast and background.....	8
Number of animals	8
8. Experimental Setup	9
Arena	9
Illumination	9
Basic Functions	11
1. Start Screen.....	11
2. Video Files and Video Sequences	12
3. ToxTrac project files	12
Project Overview	13
Calibration	14
1. Description of the calibration algorithm.....	14
2. Automatic Calibration using a Calibration Pattern.....	15
3. Simple Calibration.....	16
Draw scale lines on the image:.....	17
4. Other Functions	18
Modifying the calibration mode manually	18

- Previewing the calibration 18
- Arena definition..... 19
 - 1. Description of the Arena definition algorithm 19
 - 2. Arena definition Main Window..... 20
 - 3. Automatic Arena Definition..... 21
 - 4. Manual Arena Definition..... 22
- Draw arenas on the image: 23
- 5. Masking 24
- Draw masks on the image: 25
- 6. Zone Management..... 26
- Draw zones on the image: 27
- Detection 28
 - 1. Description of the detection algorithm 28
 - 2. Normal detection (main window)..... 29
 - 3. Advanced detection window 30
- Tracking..... 35
 - 1. Description of the Tracking algorithm 35
 - 2. Kalman tracking 36
 - 3. Texture Matching 38
 - 4. Identity Preservation..... 40
 - 5. Debug Options..... 41
- Results 42
 - 1. Statistics..... 42
 - Arenas..... 42
 - Population..... 43
 - 2. Graphical outputs screen 44
 - Arenas..... 44
 - Population..... 45

Playback	46
3. Output Files	48
Main project file (<i>pname.tox</i>)	49
Background generated image (<i>pname_Background.jpg</i>)	49
Time Stats (<i>Time.txt</i>)	49
Excel Stats file (<i>pname.xls</i>)	49
General Stats file (<i>Stats.txt</i>)	49
Tracking file (<i>Tracking.txt</i>)	50
Group file (<i>Groups.txt, GroupsIndex.txt</i>)	51
Tracking file calibrated (<i>Tracking_RealSpace.txt</i>)	51
Instantaneous speed (<i>Instant_Speed.txt</i>)	52
Instantaneous acceleration (<i>Instant_Accel.txt</i>)	52
Speed distribution (<i>Distribution_Speed.txt</i>)	53
Acceleration distribution (<i>Distribution_Accel.txt</i>)	53
Transitions (<i>Transitions.txt</i>)	54
Frozen Events (<i>FrozenEvents.txt</i>)	54
Projected trajectory (<i>Trajectory.jpeg</i>)	55
Exploration (<i>Exploration.txt, Exploration.jpeg</i>)	56
Distance to center (<i>Dist_CenterPos.txt, Dist_Center_Pos.jpeg</i>)	58
Distance to mean position (<i>Dist_MeanPos.txt, Dist_Mean_Pos.jpeg</i>)	58
Distance to edges (<i>Dist_Edges.txt, Dist_Edge_[edge].jpeg</i>)	59
Zone distance stats (<i>Dist_Zones.txt</i>)	61
References	63

Starting Guide

1. License

ToxTrac 2026. Copyright (c) 2026 Universidade da Coruña

This product includes software developed by the ToxTrac authors.

Licensed under the Apache License, Version 2.0 (the "License"); you may not use this software except in compliance with the License. You may obtain a copy of the License at:

<http://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0>

Unless required by applicable law or agreed to in writing, software distributed under the License is distributed on an "AS IS" BASIS, WITHOUT WARRANTIES OR CONDITIONS OF ANY KIND, either express or implied.

2. Recommended Citations

If you use *ToxTrac* in scientific work, please cite (Rodriguez et al., 2026a; Rodriguez et al., 2018):

- Rodriguez, A., Molaes-Ulloa, A., Andersson, M., & Brodin, T. (2026). ToxTrac 2026 (1.4). Universidade da Coruña. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20393895>.
- Rodriguez, A., Zhang, H., Klaminder, J., Brodin, T., Andersson, P. L. & Andersson, M. (2018). ToxTrac: a fast and robust software for tracking organisms. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*. 9(3):460-464. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12874>.

To cite this document use (Rodriguez et al., 2026b):

- Rodriguez, A., Molaes-Ulloa, A., Andersson, M., & Brodin, T. (2026). ToxTrac 2026 User and Technical Overview Manual. Universidade da Coruña. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20397164>.

Related Work (Panadeiro et al., 2021; Rodriguez et al., 2017):

- Panadeiro, V., Rodriguez, A., Henry, J. *et al.* A review of 28 free animal-tracking software applications: current features and limitations. *Lab Anim* **50**, 246–254 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41684-021-00811-1>.
- Rodriguez, A., Zhang, H., Klaminder, J., Brodin, T., & Andersson, M. (2017). ToxId: an algorithm to track the identity of multiple animals. *Scientific Reports*. 7(1):14774. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-15104-2>.

3. Third-party components

ToxTrac 2026 has been developed in Windows 11, in C++17 using Visual Studio 2022 with Qt Visual Studio Tools c3.3.1. Installer created with Inno Setup: <https://jrsoftware.org/isinfo.php>

This software uses third-party libraries, including:

- Qt 6.8.2 (LGPL)
- OpenCV 4.11.0 (Apache License 2.0)
- pugixml 1.11 (MIT License)
- LibXL 4.6.0 (Commercial License)

Qt libraries are dynamically linked. Users may replace or modify these libraries in accordance with the LGPL license.

See `THIRD_PARTY_NOTICES.txt` for full details.

4. Requirements

ToxTrac has been created for Windows 11, 64-bit architecture. We recommend a minimum of 16 GB of RAM. Older or inferior systems may not run *ToxTrac* properly.

ToxTrac requires the Microsoft VC++ 2015-2022 (x64) redistributables to work. Before the installation process, *ToxTrac* will try to locate the library in your system and install it if needed. This library can be downloaded and installed manually from https://aka.ms/vs/17/release/vc_redist.x64.exe

A minimum screen resolution of 1280x800 is required to display properly the interface windows.

5. Installing and running the software

The *ToxTrac* project, containing the latest software version, the documentation of the program and other resources is hosted at <https://toxtrac.sourceforge.io>.

To install *ToxTrac*, it is only necessary to execute the .exe Windows installer file provided.

Visual Studio 2015-2022 Redistributable Packages (or newer) are required to run *ToxTrac*. The installer will try to download and install this component automatically, if necessary, it also can be installed from https://aka.ms/vs/17/release/vc_redist.x64.exe.

Once Visual Studio or the Visual C++ Redistributable Package is installed, follow the instructions of the install process. *ToxTrac* and all necessary components will be installed in the selected folder and a shortcut in the start menu will be created (a shortcut in the desktop may not be installed). Now *ToxTrac* is ready.

An updated codec pack is recommended to properly handle video files with *ToxTrac*. We have used K-Lite Codec Pack, available at <https://www.codecguide.com>.

It is also recommendable to install any spreadsheet package compatible with .xls (Microsoft Excel files) to view the statistical file generated by *ToxTrac*.

To inspect and edit video files we recommend VirtualDub, available at <http://virtualdub.org>.

To inspect and edit image files, we recommend GIMP, available at <https://www.gimp.org>.

6. Known Issues

- *ToxTrac* is aimed at working with 96 dots per inch screens (the Microsoft Windows operating system default display). Changing the dpi, for example to increase the font size in the windows accessibility configuration, will not increase the text size. Instead, *ToxTrac* will try to rescale all text elements to avoid clipping. This behavior may result in difficulties visualizing the interface for some screens, especially in tablets or some portable devices.
- If the used file names, the project, the calibration or the video folders contain non-English characters, *ToxTrac* may not work properly.
- If the project location is in a folder without writing permission, *ToxTrac* will not be able to save the project data and may crash with or without a warning. In previous versions, some users reported crashes, when the program was trying to write on disk generally just after successfully finishing an analysis. This issue has not been detected in the current version. The specific sources of the errors as far as we know were:
 - **Source:** Using third-party antivirus (i.e. Avast) antivirus software with a module/function to protect certain folders of the system from being accessed by some programs.
 - **Solution1:** You may want to uninstall or configure the antivirus to grant *ToxTrac* permission to write on the folders).
 - **Solution2:** Try to save in a non-protected folder, generally, a folder such as *C:\toxtrac* could work.
 - **Source:** Using the built-in windows security software with the *Controlled folder Access* enabled, in the folders where *ToxTrac* is trying to write.
 - **Solution1:** Save the Project in a non-user folder (*Documents* and *Desktop* are user folders), you must set the folder before you run the tracking procedure, otherwise the autosave feature will cause the program to update the results and crash when accessing them or when attempting to write the file. (A folder such as *C:\Toxtrac* should not be restricted by the system).
 - **Solution2:** Disable the *Controlled folder Access* option or remove the folders u want to use with *ToxTrac* from the list of protected folders.
 - **Source:** The user does not have permission to use the selected folder, or the selected folder includes non-compatible characters in the path.
 - **Solution:** Check the permissions on the desired folder, the privileges of the current user and the path name of the folder.

7. Recording an experiment

Video format

ToxTrac supports a wide variety of .avi, and .mp4 video files with any resolution and framerate, including MPEG-4 and x264 compressed .avi video files. However, the video should have the highest possible quality.

ToxTrac will use only one-color channel, by default converting the video image format to a grayscale image. However, the user can decide to use different color spaces (Advanced detection).

Resolution and framerate

Video resolution should be high enough so that the body length of the animal size is at least 20 pixels, and framerate high enough so the animal area in consecutive frames overlaps. For large animals we recommend a body length not larger than 200 pixels, and a framerate enough so 80% of the animal area in consecutive frames overlaps. We find that 25fps is enough for most experiments, but with fast moving animals, and especially in multiple animals' experiments, a higher framerate may be advisable.

Contrast and background

ToxTrac will detect and track animals in rectangular pieces of the image containing the arenas where we want to observe the animals. Inside the arena, the tracking areas are defined as uniform regions with no particular shape, where the tracked objects can be detected.

The background color in the tracking areas should be as homogeneous as possible, with the highest possible contrast with the animals, as *ToxTrac* detection algorithm uses contrast to separate the animals from the background.

The easiest setup is to track bright animals over dark backgrounds or dark animals over bright backgrounds. Though a specific color channel can be used to get the contrast.

The presence of different background objects which cannot be separated from the animal by contrast alone is acceptable, with these conditions:

- Static objects can be manually filtered (masking) or filtered using background subtraction.
- Moving objects smaller or larger than the animals can be filtered out with size thresholds.

Other objects will difficult or impede the tracking process. It is especially important to use a background as free of reflections or shadows as possible (see lighting) and to exclude the dark edges of the experimental setup from the background (see arena definition).

Number of animals

Multiple animals can be tracked in the same arena; however, we don't recommend using more than 5-10 animals in a single experiment if it is important to keep the identity of the animals during the experiment. This value however depends on the occlusion degree observed in the video.

8. Experimental Setup

The experimental setup is typically formed by the arenas, the camera and the illumination elements (lights, filters, diffusers...). During an experiment, the experimental setup should be isolated from external interference and external light variations.

Figure 1. Arena schematic.

It is very important that the experimental setup presents the same conditions and it is not moved during an experiment, between the calibration and the experiment, or between experiments, if the same calibration data is used or if they are going to be processed together.

Arena

The walls of the arena should not cast strong shadows or reflections. This can be achieved by studying the camera position, the lighting conditions and the arena materials. Transparent or translucent walls will not cast shadows but may have reflections; and opaque walls will not have reflections but may cast shadows. Also, wall height can be adjusted to reduce these effects, and walls can be in most cases excluded from the tracking area.

Illumination

Without an appropriate illumination, the task of tracking is impossible. The light conditions determine the type, position, angle and intensity of the beams incident in the arenas which will be then registered by the camera.

We recommend two types of illumination to be used in the tracking system:

- Diffuse illumination, this light preserves the texture details and mitigates shadows.
- Backlight illumination, this light will highlight the shapes and will not cause shadows. However, it will also hide the textures of the objects.

A scheme of how to construct these illumination types is shown in Figure 2, and Table 1 shows how each type of light interacts with different characteristics of the objects.

Dark field (diffuse) illumination Backlight illumination

Figure 2. Dark filed and backlight illumination.

Table 1. Dark filed and backlight illumination characteristics.

Feature	Backlight	Dark Field
Absorption (Changes in light absorption from the object)	None	Minimal effect
Texture (Changes un surface texture)	None	Textured surfaces brighter than polished
Elevation (Changes in height from surface to camera, z axis)	None	Outer edges are bright
Shape (Change on shape or contour along x/y axis)	Shows outside contours	Contours highlighted, flat surfaces darker than raised
Translucency (Changes in density-related light transmission)	Shows changes in translucency vs. opaqueness	None

Basic Functions

1. Start Screen

Figure 3. Start Screen.

1: Load/save menu: “New Project” (deletes all current data, and reloads color and configuration files), “Save Project”, “Load Project” or “Merge Project” (merges another project in the current one, this requires that both projects are recorded in the same conditions, with the same calibration data and the same arena definition parameters).

2: Settings menu: Allows the user to navigate through the different settings of the software. These are divided into four different panels: “Project Overview”, “Arena Definition”, “Detection”, and “Tracking”.

3: Results menu, (only available after analyzing the video sequences), this allows the user to see the tracking results. “Statistics” for statistical data; and “Graphical Outputs” for visual results and summaries.

4: Track/Stop, Process the videos with the current configuration. It automatically saves the project when the analysis starts and when it finishes. During the analysis, this button will allow the user to stop at a safe point. Upon stop, all progress is lost.

5: Window menus, Standard windows buttons to minimize, maximize and close *ToxTrac* main window.

2. Video Files and Video Sequences

ToxTrac uses the concept of video sequence, to refer to a continuous recording which can be composed of multiple video files. When loading a video, *Toxtrac* will automatically try to load all the subsequent files of the sequence, and treat them as a continuous recording, with a single frame index. To this end, all the files should be placed in the same folder, and file names should end in a correlative number according to the file order (example: video01.avi, video02.avi, ...).

ToxTrac can analyze multiple video sequences (each sequence composed by multiple video files) in bulk, if configuration parameters, image conditions and experimental conditions are not changed.

3. ToxTrac project files

ToxTrac saves all configuration, results and the location of required external data, in a project file (*pname.tox*) located in the project folder (*pDir*).

A project is, therefore, a coherent tracking analysis (of one or more video sequences), defined in a project file, which can be loaded, modified and visualized, with *ToxTrac*.

ToxTrac will store additional data in the project folder; and will create a main data subfolder ("*pDir/pname/*") and an additional subfolder for each video sequence ("*pDir/pname/seqDir/*"), to store stats and tracking results. And all this data, together with the original video files, calibration is required for *ToxTrac*, to successfully load a project.

To move a project to a new folder, simply save the project into a new folder using the **load / save menu**.

To migrate a project to a different computer, we recommend storing the video and calibration data inside in the project folder and moving the entire folder with all its contents. Additionally, the paths in (*pname.tox*) may require editing to point to the new location.

Project Overview

This screen shows the selected videos to track, and allows the user to add, remove, or reorder them. In addition, the user can modify basic parameters.

Figure 4. Project overview screen.

1: Select Location: Select project location in the hard drive, all results will be saved in this folder, be sure you have writing permissions in this folder.

2: Load: Load a new video sequence in the list. To add a sequence formed of multiple videos named with correlative numbers, select the first video of the sequence and all files representing video fragments of the same video will be added to the list as a video sequence. Each sequence will be analyzed as one entity.

3: Reset Project: Removes all results, videos, and calibration data, keeping current configuration.

4: Clear Results: Remove all results computed for current videos.

5: Calibration: Open calibration window.

6: Start: Select the starting point (min/sec) in all sequences, for the analysis (*video.mIni*, *video.sIni*).

7: Finish: Select the ending point (min/sec) in all sequences, for the analysis (*video.mEnd*, *video.sEnd*).

8: List of videos and sequences: Right clicking in one of the sequences allows the user to move up or down, or to delete the corresponding sequence in the list. It also shows the status of the current video, and the completion rate of the different stages of the process.

Calibration

1. Description of the calibration algorithm

ToxTrac uses image calibration to estimate a pixel-to-real-distance conversion, to provide the user with real spatial statistics.

ToxTrac uses the Pinhole calibration model (Bradski & Kaehler, 2008). This model has an intrinsic part, independent from the view and defined by the camera matrix M , and a component dependent on the view formed by a rotation R and a translation transformation t :

$$p = M[R|t]P_w \quad (1)$$

Which expresses how the view of a scene is obtained by projecting a scene's 3D point P_w into the image plane using a perspective transformation which forms the corresponding pixel p .

Where M is defined by the focal lengths (f_x, f_y) which are expressed in pixel units and the principal point (c_x, c_y) , that is usually the image center:

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} f_x & 0 & c_x \\ 0 & f_y & c_y \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2).$$

And the rotation R and a translation transformation t are expressed:

$$[R|t] = \begin{bmatrix} r_{11} & r_{12} & r_{13} & t_x \\ r_{21} & r_{22} & r_{23} & t_y \\ r_{31} & r_{32} & r_{33} & t_z \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3).$$

Additionally, *ToxTrac* uses an extended parametric distortion model: These distortions can be modeled using the following parametric equations:

$$d(x) = x \frac{1 + k_1 r^2 + k_2 r^4 + k_3 r^6}{1 + k_4 r^2 + k_5 r^4 + k_6 r^6} + 2p_1 xy + p_2 (r^2 + 2x^2) + s_1 r^2 + s_2 r^4, \quad (4)$$

$$d(y) = y \frac{1 + k_1 r^2 + k_2 r^4 + k_3 r^6}{1 + k_4 r^2 + k_5 r^4 + k_6 r^6} + p_1 (r^2 + 2y^2) + 2p_2 xy + s_3 r^2 + s_4 r^4, \quad (5)$$

$$r^2 = x^2 + y^2, \quad (6)$$

where x and y are spatial coordinates, r is the distance to the lens optical center, $d(x)$ and $d(y)$ are the corresponding distorted coordinates, k_i are the radial distortion coefficients, p_i are the tangential distortion coefficients and s_i the prism distortion coefficients. The distortion coefficients do not depend on the scene viewed; thus, they also belong to the intrinsic camera parameters. And they remain the same regardless of the captured image resolution.

2. Automatic Calibration using a Calibration Pattern

ToxTrac calibration uses a sequence of images of a calibration pattern. The calibration images should be recorded using the same conditions as in the intended experiment and in the same image resolution.

The calibration pattern has the shape of a black and white chessboard, without edge lines and with white edges. It must be printed in high resolution and can be automatically generated in some image editing tools such as GIMP. The images should be taken in a well illuminated environment, in the plane of interest of the experiment, and using the same camera position and camera parameters as in the actual experiment. The calibration images should be placed in the same directory and with a file name ending in correlative numbers.

Figure 5. Automatic calibration.

- 1: Load Image:** load sequence of calibration images, by selecting the first image of the sequence.
- 2: Pose Menu:** selects one of the calibration images to define the camera pose.
- 3: Pattern Columns:** select the number of columns (*calibration.cols*) of the calibration pattern.
- 4: Pattern Rows:** select the number of rows (*calibration.rows*) of the calibration pattern.
- 5: Square Size:** introduce the dimensions in mm of the squares of the calibration pattern (*calibration.size*).
- 6: Distortion:** select a distortion model (*calibration.dist*), using different subsets of the distortion coefficients from equations 4-6. Available models are: “Radial 3” (dist. coeffs.: k_1, k_2, k_3), “Radial 3 + Tangential 2” (dist. coeffs.: k_1, k_2, k_3, p_1, p_2), “Radial 6 + Tangential 2” (dist. coeffs.: $k_1, k_2, k_3, p_1, p_2, k_4, k_5, k_6$), “Radial 6 + Tangential 2 + Prism 4” (dist. coeffs.: $k_1, k_2, k_3, p_1, p_2, k_4, k_5, k_6, s_1, s_2, s_3, s_4$).

7: Calibrate: attempt automatic calibration. *ToxTrac* uses a corner detection algorithm that finds the positions of all the squares in the images and then uses the known dimensions of the squares in the calibration pattern and their positions in the image to estimate the calibration parameters. If the found positions do not correspond with the number of rows (*calibration.rows*) or columns (*calibration.cols*) of the pattern for a particular image, the algorithm will show an error message, and that image should be eliminated from the sequence. If calibration is successful, it will show the detected features of the pattern.

3. Simple Calibration

Simple calibration uses a simplified version of the calibration model, assuming no lens distortion, and without needing to define rotation or translation view parameters. By allowing to set a constant scale correspondence between pixels and mm.

Figure 6. Simple calibration.

1: Option 1: mm/pixel: if the user knows the scale, can input how many pixels correspond to one millimeter in the image and press “Calibrate”. For example, a horizontal scale of 1:10 (1 mm = 10 pixel) and a vertical scale of 1:9.5 (1 mm = 9.5 pixel).

2: Option 2: pixel/mm: analogous to the previous case, inputting how many millimeters correspond to one pixel.

3: Option 3: Define Scale on Image: a simple way to measure the pixel to mm scale, is to measure the physical dimensions of the arena along two lines, draw the corresponding lines in the image, input the physical length of said lines and press “Calibrate”. *ToxTrac* will then estimate the scale automatically and calibrate the system. This method uses a module that allows the user to draw lines on the image by clicking in two points in the image with the mouse (*calibration.segmentsSimpleCalibration*) (see Figure 7).

Draw scale lines on the image:

Figure 7. Drawing scale lines on the image.

The drawing scale lines module opens a new window where the user can click and interact with the image to set a pair of points in the image, to define the required lines, one at a time. Pressing ENTER or closing the draw window, will save the defined line. The following commands are available:

LEFT-CLICK: adds an anchor point.

SHIFT + LEFT-CLICK: remove anchor point. Deletes the point in the position of the click, or, if there is no point nearby, the last point introduced.

CTRL + LEFT-CLICK: edit anchor point. Allows the user to move a selected point in the position of the click.

4. Other Functions

Modifying the calibration mode manually

Allows the user to set manually any parameter of the calibration mode. This should only be used by experts or for testing (see Figure 8).

Figure 8. Advanced calibration.

Previewing the calibration

Allows the user to see the current calibration in a visual manner (see Figure 9).

Figure 9. Preview calibration.

Arena definition

An arena is a closed and controlled area, where a tracking experiment will take place, the arena is separated physically from the outside and from other tracking arenas.

Additionally, inside each arena, the tracking area must be defined prior to the execution. The tracking area should be a uniform well illuminated area where the objects of interest will be studied. The objects of interest should appear clearly distinct and with high contrast inside the tracking area.

It is more important than areas outside the region where the objects of interest are located are not inside the tracking areas. Additionally, external objects, reflections, bubbles, shadows or interferences with walls should be ruled out if possible (see: *Contrast and background*).

1. Description of the Arena definition algorithm

ToxTrac provides an arena definition semiautomatic algorithm to define the arenas and tracking areas. The arena selection algorithm takes a sample image from an input video sequence to define the different tracking areas. The arena definition process is as follows:

1. The user selects one frame of the video sequence to use as reference for the algorithm.
2. After the image has been obtained, the calibration model is used to create a distortion map for every pixel of the image, and then interpolation is used to create a distortion-free image. Then image is converted to a 8-bit grayscale and normalized to value of 0-255. (**NOTE:** Current arena definition algorithm does not work in alternate color spaces).
3. Segmentation: The objective of this operation is to separate the tracking areas, which are uniform regions of the images. First, an intensity range (*roi.thr2* to *roi.thr1*) is selected by the user, separating the image into two binary sets. Finally, a closing mathematical morphological operation is executed to remove the holes and imperfections on the area selected by the previous operations.
4. Arena and area creation: First, the areas obtained in the previous step are filtered according to their size (*roi.mins*). Then, the resulting areas which possess an arbitrary shape are approximated by a polygon so that the number of vertices is the smaller possible and the distance between vertices is less or equal to the precision specified by the user (*roi.poly*). This step simplifies the shape of the selected area and helps to eliminate some irregularities at the edges. These polygons will constitute tracking areas. Finally, arenas are defined as the minimum rectangular regions in the image containing each one of the tracking areas.

In the application each arena will be defined as image region, containing a polygonal tracking area. Arenas are obtained by a map describing the undistorted positions of their pixels. Each arena constitutes unit processed in parallel with an independent tracking algorithm.

2. Arena definition Main Window

Figure 10. Arena definition.

- 1: Select sequence:** navigate through video sequences.
- 2: Select Arena:** navigate through the defined arenas (arenas are applied to all sequences).
- 3: Name:** name the current arena (*arenaRoi.arenasName*).
- 4: Toggle Arena:** enable or disable the operation of the current arena (*arenaRoi.arenasEnabled*).
- 5: Mode of Arena Definition:** select between the different modes of arena definition, options are “Manual” and “Automatic selection” (*arenaRoi.mode*).
- 6: Arena Definition:** open the arena definition dialog, corresponding to the selected mode.
- 7: Arena Masking:** open the arena masking dialog.
- 8: Zone Management:** open the zone management dialog.

3. Automatic Arena Definition

Figure 11. Automatic arena definition.

- 1: Thresholding:** select an intensity range (*arenaRoi.thr2* to *arenaRoi.thr1*), to separate the tracking in the selected arena image. Intensity is normalized to 1-255 (grayscale).
- 2: Select sequence.**
- 3: Change reference frame:** select a new reference frame in the current video sequence as base for the arena definition algorithm. This frame will be used to reconstruct the arenas by the software in this sequence.
- 4: Arena Size:** select a size threshold (*arenaRoi.mins*), the minimum number of pixels to constitute a tracking area, to filter detected arenas by size.
- 5: Arena Borders:** enable or disable the overlay visualization of the arena borders.

4. Manual Arena Definition

The user can, alternatively, draw manually in the image a rectangle to define each arena, and select the tracking area accordingly.

Figure 12. Manual arena definition.

1: Thresholding: select an intensity range ($arenaRoi.thr2$ to $arenaRoi.thr1$), to separate the tracking in the selected arena image. Intensity is normalized to 1-255 (grayscale).

2: Select sequence.

3: Change reference frame: select a new reference frame in the current video sequence as base for the arena definition algorithm. This frame will be used to reconstruct the arenas by the software in this sequence.

4: Select Arena: navigate through the defined arenas (arenas are applied to all sequences). The current arena will be shown with a green border if the **Arena Borders**, options is activated, and the corresponding tracking area will be painted red. Other masks will be shown with blue borders and soft green tracking areas.

5: Edit Arena: opens a drawing window that allows the redrawing (and replacement) of the current arena (see Figure 13).

6: Add Arena: opens a drawing window that allows drawing a new arena which will be added to the previous ones (see Figure 13).

7: Remove Arena: removes the current arena.

8: Clear Arenas: remove all arenas.

9: Arena Borders: enable or disable the overlay visualization of the arena borders.

10: Circular Arena: allows the use of circular Tracking Areas. Fits the tracking areas to their minimum enclosing circles and selecting a value to reduce the radius of the circles (*arenaRoi.fitE*, *arenaRoi.redR*).

Draw arenas on the image:

Figure 13. Drawing arenas.

The drawing arenas module opens a new window where the user can click and drag to select a new rectangular area. Pressing ENTER or closing the draw window, will save the defined arena.

5. Masking

Figure 14. Masking.

1: Select sequence.

2: Select Arena: navigate through the defined arenas (arenas are applied to all sequences). The image of the current arena will be displayed with the regions outside the tracking area painted in soft green, while the regions included in the tracked area will show the image gray value.

3: Change reference frame: select a new reference frame in the current video sequence to draw the masks over. This frame is for visualization only.

4: Select Mask: navigate through the defined masks. The current mask will be painted with a green border, and the area will be painted in soft green or with the gray color of the image depending on how affects the tracking area. Other masks will be shown with blue borders.

5: Remove Mask: remove the current mask.

6: Clear all Masks: remove all masks.

7: Add Polynomial: opens a drawing window that allows drawing a new mask which will be added to the previous ones, using a polygonal shape with at least 3 points (see Figure 15).

8: Add Circle: opens a drawing window that allows drawing a new mask which will be added to the previous ones, using a circular shape with at least 3 points (see Figure 15).

9: **Mask Type:** select the mask type. Available options are: “Remove Mask from Tracking Area”, “Add Mask to Tracking Area”, “Mask AND Tracking Area”.

Draw masks on the image:

Figure 15. Drawing masks.

The drawing module opens a new window where the user can click and interact with the image to set a set of points in the image, to define a polygon in the image, which will mark a mask over the arena. Pressing ENTER or closing the draw window, will save the defined mask. The following commands are available:

LEFT-CLICK: Adds a point.

SHIFT + LEFT-CLICK: remove anchor point. Deletes the point in the position of the click, or, if there is no point nearby, the last point introduced.

CTRL + LEFT-CLICK: edit anchor point. Allows the user to move a selected point in the position of the click.

6. Zone Management

Figure 16. Zone Management.

1: Select sequence.

2: Select Arena.

3: Change reference frame: select a new reference frame in the current video sequence to draw the zones of interest over. This is for visualization only.

4: Select Zone: navigate through the defined zones. The current zone will be painted in green with its current geometry, while others will be shown in blue.

5: Remove Zone: remove the current zone.

6: Clear all Zones: remove all zones.

7: Add Polynomial: opens a drawing window that allows drawing a new zone which will be added to the previous ones, using a polygonal shape with at least 3 points (see Figure 17).

8: Add Circle: opens a drawing window that allows drawing a new zone which will be added to the previous ones, using a circular shape with at least 3 points (see Figure 17).

9: Add Point: opens a drawing window that allows drawing a new zone which will be added to the previous ones, using a single point.

10: Add Line: opens a drawing window that allows drawing a new zone which will be added to the previous ones, in the shape of a line formed by 2 points.

Draw zones on the image:

Figure 17. Drawing zones.

The drawing module opens a new window where the user can click and interact with the image to set a set of points in the image, to define zone in the image as a single point, a line formed by 2 points, a polygon or circle formed by 3 or more points. Pressing ENTER or closing the draw window will save the defined zone. The following commands are available:

LEFT-CLICK: Adds a point.

SHIFT + LEFT-CLICK: remove anchor point. Deletes the point in the position of the click, or, if there is no point nearby, the last point introduced.

CTRL + LEFT-CLICK: edit anchor point. Allows the user to move a selected point in the position of the click.

Detection

1. Description of the detection algorithm

This dialog should be used to separate as clearly as possible the animals from the background using the threshold slider. The goal is to ensure all animals are detected in all or most frames, and that no background region is selected in any frame as an animal. The filter parameters should be set to discard any remaining nonanimal object from the detection and to filter out animal overlapping.

If the tracking area still contains some objects that cannot be separated from the animals. The user should use manual masking or background subtraction to filter them out. Background subtraction can also be used if there is not enough contrast to separate the background from the animals.

The algorithm to detect the animals in the tracking areas is defined as follows:

1. **Preprocessing:** By default, the image is converted to grayscale and normalized to the 0-255 interval. In the advanced settings, the user can change the color space, remove the normalization or add a gaussian blur operation.
2. **Background subtraction:** Disabled by default. In the advanced settings the user can load a static image as background, use a specific still frame as background, or generate a background as a frame average. Background subtraction will help the detection algorithm, by using the difference of each frame with the background as a basis to create a mask that will remove static objects from the detection (Piccardi, 2004).
3. **Threshold:** Mandatory. Uses an intensity range, in the selected color space, in the current frame, to separate the animals from the background. If background subtraction is used, the background mask will be applied to the result.
4. **Postprocess:** By default, an opening morphological operation is executed to correct geometrical imperfections in the detected animal shapes. In the advanced settings, the user can remove this operation or add different morphological operations to the pipeline.
5. **Filtering:** By default, an area filtering operation is executed to filter out detections outside a selected range. In the advanced settings, the user can remove this operation or add different filters.

2. Normal detection (main window)

Figure 18. Normal detection (main window).

- 1: Select frame:** select a frame in the current video sequence and arena to display. The user can use the slider or directly type the frame number.
- 2: Select sequence.**
- 3: Select Arena.**
- 4: Thresholding:** select an intensity range (*detection.threshold.thr2* to *detection.threshold.thr1*), in the selected color space in the current frame to separate the animals from the background. Intensity is normalized to 1-255 (grayscale).
- 5: Size filtering:** select a size range to filter out detections outside said range.
- 6: Result image:** displays the detected objects for the selected frame, video sequence and arena, with the current configuration. Each separate object is displayed in a different color. (The specific color is random).
- 7: Advanced detection:** opens the advanced detection settings window.
- 8: Display mode:** select a display mode which allows the user to view the video frame, the arena frame, the detection results in the arena, and the filtered detection results in the arena. (NOTE: this does not affect the tracking).
- 9: Navigation controls.**

10: Size information: displays the minimum, maximum, average and standard deviation of the size of the selected objects. Is affected by the selected display mode.

3. Advanced detection window

Figure 19. Advanced detection: Preprocess.

1: Select frame.

2: Select sequence.

3: Select color mode: selects the color space (color channel) for the tracking algorithm to operate (*detection.preprocess_color.type*).

4: Preprocessing operations: the list of preprocessing operations currently active. The user can right-click on the list to rearrange and erase any operation from the list (*detection.detection_preprocess_Ops*).

5: Preprocessing operation parameters: allows the user to modify the parameters of the selected operation. The operation will not be active, till saved (modifies an operation on the list), or added to the list.

6: Previous image: displays the selected frame for the selected video sequence from the original video, in the original color format.

7: Result image: displays the preprocessed frame for the selected video sequence. Each separated object is displayed in a different color. (The specific color is random).

8: Navigation controls.

Figure 20. Advanced detection: Background.

1: Select frame.

2: Select sequence.

3: Select Arena.

4: Background mode: select a background subtraction mode. Available modes are: “No Background”, “Still Frame” (*detection.background.staticFrame*, *detection.background.staticSeq*), “Averaged Background” () and “Load Background” (*detection.background.backgroundPath*).

5: Background parameters: these are specific to the selected background mode. Allow the user to set or remove the background.

6: Background image: displays the current estimated background (black if background is disabled).

7: Subtracted Thresholding: a slider to select an intensity range (from *detection.background.thr2* to *detection.background.thr1*), to separate the subtracted image (the current frame minus the background) into background (black), and possible animals (white). This information will be used to remove any detection corresponding to the background (black region of the mask). The threshold range, therefore, should be selected to remove false negatives, but can leave in the white region parts of the background without negative effects in the detection.

8: Dynamic Update: enables new frames to update the previous background using a weighted average, recommended for experts only (*detection.background.dynamic*, *detection.background.dynamicRate*).

9: Previous image: displays the selected frame, for the selected video sequence and arena, after the preprocessing detection stage.

10: Background mask: displays the estimated background mask, estimating by thresholding the difference of each frame with the background. Used to remove static objects in the regions labelled as background (black region of the mask) from the detection. (NOTE: the effects of dynamical background updates are not displayed).

11: Navigation controls.

Figure 21. Advanced detection: Threshold.

1: Select frame.

2: Select sequence.

3: Select Arena.

4: Thresholding: select an intensity range (*detection.threshold.thr2* to *detection.threshold.thr1*), in the selected color space in the current frame to separate the animals from the background. Intensity is normalized to 1-255. If background subtraction is used, the background mask will be applied to the result to remove static objects from the detection.

5: Size distribution: a chart of the size distribution of the detected objects.

6: Previous image: displays the selected frame for the selected video sequence and arena, after the preprocessing detection stage.

7: **Result image:** displays the detected objects for the selected frame, video sequence and arena. Each separated object is displayed in a different color. (The specific color is random).

8: **Navigation controls.**

Figure 22. Advanced detection: Postprocess.

1: **Select frame.**

2: **Select sequence.**

3: **Select Arena.**

4: **Postprocessing operation parameters:** allows the user to modify the parameters of the selected operation. The operation will not be active, till saved (modifies an operation on the list), or added to the list.

5: **Postprocessing operations:** the list of postprocessing operations currently active. The user can right-click on the list to rearrange and erase any operation from the list (*detection.detection_postprocess_Ops*).

6: **Size distribution:** a chart of the size distribution of the detected objects.

7: **Previous image:** displays the selected frame for the selected video sequence and arena, after the threshold stage.

8: **Result image:** displays the detected objects for the selected frame, video sequence and arena. After applying the selected postprocessing operations.

9: **Navigation controls.**

Figure 23. Advanced detection: Filter.

- 1: Select frame.**
- 2: Select sequence.**
- 3: Select Arena.**
- 4: Filtering operation parameters:** allows the user to modify the parameters of the selected operation. The operation will not be active, till saved (modifies an operation on the list), or added to the list.
- 5: Filtering operations:** the list of filtering operations currently active. The user can right-click on the list to rearrange and erase any operation from the list (*detection.detection_filter_Ops*).
- 6: Size distribution:** a chart of the size distribution of the detected objects.
- 7: Previous image:** displays the selected frame for the selected video sequence and arena, after the postprocessing stage.
- 8: Result image:** displays the detected objects for the selected frame, video sequence and arena. After applying the selected filtering operations.
- 9: Navigation controls.**

Tracking

Tracking associates the animals detected in each frame with different individuals, forming structures called tracks, which contain sets of detections that are estimated to belong to the same animal.

The tracking algorithm of *ToxTrac* is designed to minimize identity swaps (errors caused by assigning detections to the wrong animals) by detecting ambiguous situations and fragmenting tracks when there is not enough information to reliably determine which detection belongs to which animal.

The tracking algorithm requires filtering out overlapping animals during the detection stage, avoiding foreign objects being detected as animals, and defining the number of animals before the experiment starts. Several additional parameters can also affect tracking performance.

1. Description of the Tracking algorithm

The tracking algorithm of *ToxTrac* operates as follows.

1. The tracking algorithm receives, for each frame, both the image itself and information about the detected animals in that frame. This information includes the bounding box, center of mass, body orientation and additional features such as object size and shape.
2. If no previous tracks exist, a new track is created for each detected animal. Each track is associated with a Kalman filter (Bishop & Welch, 2001). The Kalman filter estimates the most probable position of the animal in the next frame according to a motion model, typically assuming approximately constant speed or acceleration. Predicted positions are treated with lower confidence than confirmed detections.
3. For each frame, the distance cost between predicted track positions and current detections is computed. An Hungarian optimization algorithm (Kuhn, 1955) is then used to associate tracks with detections while minimizing the global assignment cost. Assignments are rejected if the displacement exceeds a user-defined maximum allowed movement between frames. Additional validation criteria, such as abrupt changes in body size or body length, may also reject assignments.
4. Tracks that cannot be assigned to a detection may optionally enter a texture matching stage. In this stage, the last confirmed appearance of the animal is searched within the neighborhood of the predicted position. Candidate displacements and rotations are evaluated using a cross-correlation similarity metric between the previous animal image and the current frame. To reduce computational cost, the algorithm uses a coarse-to-fine pyramidal approach, progressively refining the search from low to high image resolution while reducing the search area. Additionally, similarity is estimated from representative sample regions instead of evaluating the entire image template at full resolution for every candidate position. Candidate texture matches are additionally filtered using consistency criteria such as maximum displacement, overlap constraints and ambiguity detection between nearby tracks. This filtering stage is intended to reduce identity swaps during close interactions or partial occlusions.
5. A collision and ambiguity detection stage analyses situations in which multiple animals are too close, partially overlapping, or generate ambiguous assignments. In these cases, tracks may be temporarily marked as ambiguous or fragmented in order to reduce the probability of identity swaps. The algorithm is intentionally designed to prioritize identity reliability over maintaining uninterrupted trajectories.

6. New tracks are created for unassigned detections.
7. Tracks remaining unassigned for too long, or tracks marked for fragmentation, are closed and stored.
8. After tracking is completed, an optional post-identification stage can be applied to reconnect fragmented trajectories and improve long-term identity consistency. This stage analyses spatial, temporal and appearance-based relationships between tracks in order to estimate whether different trajectory fragments likely belong to the same animal.

2. Kalman tracking

Figure 24. Tracking parameters: Kalman tracking.

1: Individuals / Arena: sets the number of animals in the experiment. This number is a maximum limit on the number of active tracks in each frame. If set to zero, every new detection will create a track(*kal.dNTr*).

2: Max Displacement / Frame: maximum allowed distance in pixels an animal is allowed to move each frame. This distance is also used to recognize ambiguous situations. If set to zero this value is automatically estimated as a function of its body length. However, is recommended that the user sets this parameter manually. (*kal.disF*).

3: Advanced Options: enables setting the advanced options and sets default options.

4: Max size change: allowed rate of change in size, measured as the perimeter of the animal in the image (*kal.szCh*).

5: Max Body Length Change: allowed rate of change in body length, measured as the maximum axis of its bounding box (*kal.bLCh*).

6: Max Overlap: allowed rate of overlapping between two animals, measured from the area of the bounding boxes (*kal.maxOverlap*).

7: Max Undetected: maximum number of frames without detection before closing a track (*kal.dUnd*).

8: Min Age: minimum age for a track to be considered stable. Not stable tracks do not undergo texture matching and are closed if not assigned to any blob (*kal.dAge*).

3. Texture Matching

Figure 25. Tracking parameters: Texture matching.

- 1: Enable Texture Tracking**: enables the texture matching stage for tracks that could not be associated using standard blob tracking (*texturem.enable*).
- 2: Template Size**: size of the image template used for texture matching. If set to 0, the template size will be estimated automatically from the detected animal size (*texturem.templateSize*).
- 3: Refresh Template**: number of frames before updating the stored template image of the animal during texture tracking. Lower values adapt faster to appearance changes but may increase drift. If set to zero, only the last confirmed detected image will be used (*texturem.matchRefresh*).
- 4: Advanced Options**: enables setting the advanced options and sets default options.
- 5: Patch size**: radius in pixels of the local image patches used during texture comparison, if set to zero only the sample points will be used (*texturem.patchSize*).
- 6: Main Axis Samples**: maximum number of sampling points distributed along the main axis of the animal body during texture matching (*texturem.patchSampleMainAxis*).
- 7: Sec. Axis Samples**: maximum number of sampling lines distributed along the secondary axis of the animal body during texture matching (*texturem.patchSampleSecAxis*).
- 8: Sampling Distance**: distance between sampling points used for texture matching. If set to 0, the distance will be estimated automatically (*texturem.patchSampleDist*).

- 9: Enable decomposition**: enables multi-scale coarse-to-fine texture matching in order to improve robustness and speed for large animals or large search areas (*texturem.activateCoarse*).
- 10: Target Size**: target size of the animal template during the coarse decomposition stage. Smaller values increase speed but may reduce precision (*texturem.coarseTemplateSize*).
- 11: Step Reduction**: scale reduction factor applied between decomposition levels during coarse texture matching (*texturem.coarseReduction*).
- 12: Max Search Radius**: maximum search radius used during texture matching. If set to 0, the radius will be estimated automatically from the Max. displacement per frame setting, which can in turn be estimated from the animal size and motion model (*texturem.matchSearchRadiusMax*).
- 13: Matching Threshold**: minimum similarity score required to accept a texture matching result (*texturem.matchThreshold*).
- 14: Max Rotation**: maximum rotation angle explored during texture matching, in degrees (*texturem.matchRotMax*).
- 15: Rotation Step**: angular step, in degrees, used to test different rotations during texture matching (*texturem.matchRotStep*).

4. Identity Preservation

Figure 26. Tracking parameters: Identity preservation.

- 1: ID Algorithm:** identity preservation algorithm, available options are “No Id”, which disables identity preservation, and “Histogram CQ”, which computes identity preservation using histogram and hu moments correlation (*kam.idAl*).
- 2: Advanced Options:** enables setting the advanced options and sets default options.
- 3: Use Average:** use a mean metric instead of a max similarity value (*kam.mAvg*) (Recommended).
- 4: Use Histogram Correlation Distribution:** use correlation of histograms for similarity (*kam.corH*).
- 5: History:** maximum number of samples used for every track in the algorithm. This parameter also affects significantly the memory and time used by the fragment identification algorithm (*kam.mAvg*).
- 6: Comparisons:** limits the number of comparisons between two samples of the same track in order to increase speed (*kam.mCmp*).
- 7: Histogram Size:** number of bins in the histogram for each animal detection. If set to 0, this value will be estimated automatically, recommended) (*kam.hisS*).
- 8: Short Fragments:** minimum track size to be used by the algorithm, smaller tracks will not be saved (*kam.mnSS*).
- 9: Long Fragments:** minimum track size to classify track as long (*kam.mnLS*).

5. Debug Options

Figure 27. Tracking parameters: Debug options.

- 1: Enable track debugging:** enables generation of detailed debugging information for track assignment, conflicts and lifecycle events during tracking (*debug.debug_track_enable*).
- 2: Enable texture matching debugging:** enables generation of detailed debugging images and information for the texture matching stage, including templates, matching maps and sampled points (*debug.debug_tm_enable*).
- 3: Track:** track identifier used to filter debugging output to a specific track. If set to a negative value, all tracks will be processed (*debug.debug_trackId*).
- 4: Frame Start:** first frame index where debugging information will be generated, if set to a negative value no restriction is applied (*debug.debug_frameIni*).
- 5: Frame End:** last frame index where debugging information will be generated, if set to a negative value no restriction is applied (*debug.debug_frameEnd*).

Results

1. Statistics

Arenas

Figure 28. Statistics: Arenas.

1: Select sequence.

2: Select Arena.

3: Advanced Options: enables setting the advanced options.

4: Sampling Parameters: select temporal (*analysis.samT*) and distance (*analysis.samD*) sampling values to control how movement distance is measured from the tracked trajectory. *samT* defines the temporal sampling interval used to compare positions, while *samD* ignores very small displacements that are likely caused by tracking noise or small oscillations. Together, these parameters help smooth the measured trajectory and avoid overestimating traveled distance. This is related to the well-known “coastline paradox”: the finer the measurement scale, the longer and noisier a path appears. Using larger sampling intervals or minimum movement thresholds produces more stable and biologically meaningful distance estimates.

5: Mobility Parameters: allows the user to change the speed threshold to estimate the mobility rate of the animal in the stats (*analysis.mbSp*).

6: Frozen Events Parameters: a frozen event is detected when the animal has moved less than a distance in mm, in a time interval in seconds. These settings allow the user to change these thresholds to calculate the frozen events (*analysis.fmmT, analysis.fTim*).

7: Transition Parameters: a transition is detected when the time between two consecutive detections exceed this value, signaling a period when the animal is not visible. This setting allows the user to change the time threshold (in seconds) to calculate a transition (*analysis.mnTT*).

8: Stats Screen: displays the tracking statistics for the selected video sequence and arena.

9: Save Results: saves all results in the output folder.

Population

Figure 29. Statistics: Population.

1: Stats Screen: displays the tracking statistics for the entire population.

2. Graphical outputs screen

Arenas

Figure 30. Graphical Outputs: Arenas.

1: Output: select the graphical output to display in the visualization panel, representing different stats of the tracked animals in the current video sequence and arena. Available options are: "Trajectory" (displays all trajectories), "North Edge" (spatial distribution in relation to the upper limit of the arena), "West Edge" (spatial distribution in relation to the left limit of the arena), "South Edge" (spatial distribution in relation to the bottom limit of the arena), "East Edge" (spatial distribution in relation to the right limit of the arena), "All Edges" (spatial distribution in relation to the closest edge of the arena), "Exploration" (spatial distribution in a grid of selected size), "Center Point Dist." (spatial distribution in relation to center of the arena), "Mean Point Dist." (spatial distribution in relation to median of all detected positions), "Plain Output".

2: Select sequence.

3: Select Arena.

4: Zone Size: change the zone size in mm. This will affect most statistics like the grid size for the exploration output, or the bin size for all spatial distributions (*analysis.zSiz*).

5: Num Zones: changes the number of bins (*analysis.nZon*) used in the edge statistics. The distribution is divided into $nZon - 1$ zones of the selected size, representing increasing distances from the edge. All detections beyond the last zone are grouped into the final remaining bin.

6: Normalize Arena: if enabled, the zones will be computed according to the extremes of the detected positions instead of using the full image (*analysis.norm*).

7: Smoothing and Interpolation: (*analysis.smoo*, *analysis.int1*, *analysis.int2*, *analysis.int3*).

8: Visualization Panel: displays the selected graphical output for the video sequence and arena, with the selected configuration.

Population

Figure 31. Graphical Outputs: Population.

1: Output: select the graphical output to display in the visualization panel, representing different stats of the tracked animals in all sequences and arenas projected in the same virtual space. Available options are: "**Trajectory**" (displays all trajectories), "**North Edge**" (spatial distribution in relation to the upper limit of the virtual space), "**West Edge**" (spatial distribution in relation to the left limit of the virtual space), "**South Edge**" (spatial distribution in relation to the bottom limit of the virtual space), "**East Edge**" (spatial distribution in relation to the right limit of the virtual space), "**All Edges**" (spatial distribution in relation to the closest edge of the virtual space), "**Exploration**" (spatial distribution in a grid of selected size of the virtual space), "**Center Point Dist.**" (spatial distribution in relation to center of the virtual space), "**Mean Point Dist.**" (spatial distribution in relation to median of all detected positions in the virtual space), "**Plain Output**".

4: Zone Size: change the zone size in mm. This will affect most statistics like the grid size for the exploration output, or the bin size for all spatial distributions (*analysis.zSiz*).

5: Num Zones: changes the number of bins (analysis.nZon) used in the edge statistics. The distribution is divided into nZon - 1 zones of the selected size, representing increasing distances from the edge. All detections beyond the last zone are grouped into the final remaining bin.

6: Normalize Arena: if enabled, the zones will be computed according to the extremes of the detected positions instead of using the full image (*analysis.norm*).

8: Visualization Panel: displays the selected graphic in a real scale virtual arena, projecting together the results of the entire population.

Playback

Figure 32. Graphical Outputs: Playback.

1: Select frame.

2: Select sequence.

3: Select Arena.

4: Color coding: select how to color the tracking results. Available options are: “**By track number**” (animals are colored according to their track number), “**By detection type**” (animals are colored in green for the Hungarian algorithm, yellow for the texture matching algorithm or in red for predicted positions).

5: Visual Options: enables or disables different visual overlays like identity numbers or bounding boxes. Also allows the user to display the tracking results over the preprocessed frame or the unprocessed video frame (the original color space of the video).

6: Video Frame Selection: controls that allow selecting an initial and final frame to export a video with the tracking results.

7: Create Video: select the file location and file name to export a video with the tracking results using the selected display mode, color coding and visual options.

8: Display mode: select a display mode which allows the user to visualize the tracking results in the coordinate system of the video frame or the arena.

9: Navigation controls and frame playback.

10: Visualization Panel: displays the tracking results with the selected visual options for the selected frame, video sequence and arena.

3. Output Files

The application automatically generates a folder structure to save the results of the tracking. A set of files are generated to save the project configuration data. The main results of the project, containing the majority of the statistical data generated for each individual and the population will be formatted in a datasheet (Figure 4). Additionally, a set of files is created with the results for the entire population and another set of files is created with the results for each arena and sequence. The creation of most of these files can be enabled or disabled in the *Configuration.txt* file. When analyzing a project, a folder is generated for every video sequence and the corresponding file names are named ending in a number representing the arena number.

The general Structure of the project folder will be:

<i>project folder (pDir/)</i>		
main project file	: (pname)	: [.txt]
background generated image	: (pname_Background)	: [.jpg]
excel stats file	: (pname)	: [.xls]
<i>main data folder (pname/)</i>		
time stats	: (Time)	: [.txt]
general stats	: (Stats)	: [.txt]
population stats: tracking file calibrated	: (Tracking_RealSpace)	: [.txt]
population stats: instantaneous speed	: (Instant_Speed)	: [.txt]
population stats: instantaneous acceleration	: (Instant_Accel)	: [.txt]
population stats: speed distribution	: (Distribution_Speed)	: [.txt]
population stats: acceleration distribution	: (Distribution_Accel)	: [.txt]
population stats: transitions	: (Transitions)	: [.txt]
population stats: frozen events	: (FrozenEvents)	: [.txt]
population stats: projected trajectory	: (Trajectory)	: [.jpg]
population stats: exploration	: (Exploration)	: [.txt, .jpg]
population stats: distance to center	: (Dist_CenterPos)	: [.txt, .jpg]
population stats: distance to mean position	: (Dist_MeanPos)	: [.txt, .jpg]
population stats: distance to edges	: (Dist_Edge)	: [.txt, .jpg]
<i>video sequence folder (seqDir/)</i>		
arena output: tracking file	: (Tracking_1)	: [.txt]
arena output: group file	: (Groups_1)	: [.txt]
arena output: group file index	: (GroupsIndex_1)	: [.txt]
arena stats: tracking file calibrated	: (Tracking_RealSpace_1)	: [.txt]
arena stats: instantaneous speed	: (Instant_Speed_1)	: [.txt]
arena stats: instantaneous acceleration	: (Instant_Accel_1)	: [.txt]
arena stats: speed distribution	: (Distribution_Speed_1)	: [.txt]
arena stats: acceleration distribution	: (Distribution_Accel_1)	: [.txt]
arena stat: transitions	: (Transitions_1)	: [.txt]
arena stat: frozen events	: (FrozenEvents_1)	: [.txt]
arena stats: projected trajectory	: (Trajectory_1)	: [.jpg]
arena stats: exploration	: (Exploration_1)	: [.txt, .jpg]
arena stats: distance to center	: (Dist_CenterPos_1)	: [.txt, .jpg]
arena stats: distance to mean position	: (Dist_MeanPos_1)	: [.txt, .jpg]
arena stats: distance to edges	: (Dist_Edge_1)	: [.txt, .jpg]
arena stats: zone distance stats	: (Dist_Zones_1)	: [.txt]

Main project file (*pname.tox*)

The main project file in has the *.tox* extension and can be opened by *ToxTrac*. It is a text file in *.xml* format generated by *ToxTrac*. Can be used to load a project and add a project into another compatible project, joining both populations.

The main project file contains required file locations, configuration parameters that can be edited in a text editor, calibration matrices, arena definitions, and others.

Background generated image (*pname_Background.jpg*)

Contains a background image used for Background Subtraction, generated by *ToxTrac*.

Time Stats (*Time.txt*)

A text file generated by *ToxTrac* that contains the tracking processing time in format (*hh:mm:ss*).

Excel Stats file (*pname.xls*)

A text file generated by *ToxTrac* that contains a comprehensive summary of all statistics.

It is formed by sheet where all population stats are summarized, by projecting all arenas off all sequences into a common virtual arena and a sheet with the stats of every arena and video sequence.

Includes the formatted information of every other results file.

General Stats file (*Stats.txt*)

The *Stats.txt* files represent a summary of the main behavioral and movement statistics obtained from the tracking data.

The analysis includes preprocessing steps such as interpolation, smoothing, and spatial calibration, followed by the computation of movement, visibility, exploration, transition, and freezing statistics.

The generated output files contain summarized information for the population and each arena (see Table 3), including:

- Video and arena information.
- Arena geometry and calibrated dimensions.
- Mean animal position and arena center.
- Average speed and acceleration.
- Mobility and visibility statistics.
- Exploration metrics and explored area coverage.
- Total travelled distance.
- Transition counts between regions or visibility states.

- Freezing event statistics including number and duration of events.

Table 2. *Stats.txt* content.

Video Resolution:	[320 x 240]	
Video FrameRate:	30	
Analysed Video Frames:	9000	
Analysed Video Time:	300	
Arena:	[17.1458, 16.9671], [193.135, 16.9671], [17.1458, 188.083], [193.135, 188.083] [17.1458, 16.9671, 1], [192.135, 16.9671, 1], [17.1458, 187.083, 1], [192.135, 187.083, 1]	
Arena Center:	[87.4946, 85.0579]	
Mean Position:	[82.7616, 86.2684]	
Av. Speed:	38.075	0
Mob. Av. Speed:	38.6749	0
Av. Accel:	157.172	0
Mobility Rate:	0.984278	0
Visible Frames:	8931	0
Visible Time:	297.7	0
Invisible Frames:	69	0
Invisible Time:	2.3	0
First Visible Frame:	0	0
Last Visible Frame:	9000	0
Visibility Rate:	0.992333	0
Invisibility Rate:	0.00766667	0
Explored Areas:	61	0
Number of Areas:	81	0
Exploration Rate:	0.753086	0
Total Distance:	11511.4	0
Transitions to White:	37	0
Transitions to Black:	37	0
Number of Frozen Events:	0	0
Total Time Frozen:	0	0
Average Time Frozen:	0	0

Tracking file (*Tracking.txt*)

Raw tracking information as calculated by the tracker algorithm, with animal positions and bounding boxes in pixel coordinates related to the arena; and temporal coordinates in frames.

Pixel coordinates are relative to the arena space and after removing distortion. So they cannot be back-projected directly to the original images. Time coordinates are in frames (Table 4, Table 5).

This file is required by *ToxTrac* to calculate all results.

Table 3. *Tracking.txt* content.

Frame	Arena	Track	x	y	Box angle	Box X	Box Y	Box width	Box height	label
0	0	1	145.826	162.29	26.5651	145.2	161.1	29.9633	12.522	1
1	0	1	143.924	162.02	23.9625	143.18	160.969	30.1558	12.5903	1
2	0	1	141.487	161.6	8.1301	140.42	162.06	29.9813	12.4451	1
3	0	1	138.581	161.362	16.6992	137.945	161.184	31.6083	12.0686	1
4	0	1	136.395	161.215	15.2551	135.454	161.169	30.6093	11.6649	1

Table 4. Label Interpretation.

Label	Meaning
0	Position predicted by the Kalman Filter.
1	Position of an animal detected in the image assigned to the track by the Hungarian algorithm.
2	Position assigned by the Texture Matching Algorithm (without an animal being detected in the image)
3	Interpolated position.

Group file (*Groups.txt*, *GroupsIndex.txt*)

Generated for each arena. This is a text file that identifies groups of tracks when all the animals are present in the corresponding sequence and arena in format: (Group - Number of Animals – track1 – track2 – track 3 - ..., see Table 6).

Table 5. *Groups.txt* content.

Number of groups:	4
List of tracks forming each group:	3 1 2 3 3 46 48 49 3 46 52 53 3 46 52 54

Tracking file calibrated (*Tracking_RealSpace.txt*)

Text file with the calibrated tracking information, with animal positions un mm coordinates related to the arena; and temporal coordinates in seconds (Table 7).

The file generated for the population also contains the video sequence information.

Table 6. *Tracking_RealSpace.txt* content.

Time (sec)	Arena	Track	Pos. X (mm)	Pos. Y (mm)	Label
0	1	1	225.826	186.29	1
0.0333333	1	1	223.924	186.02	1
0.0666667	1	1	221.487	185.6	1
0.1	1	1	218.581	185.362	1
0.133333	1	1	216.395	185.215	1

Instantaneous speed (*Instant_Speed.txt*)

This file shows the acceleration of the animals in each instant as first derivate of the *Tracking_RealSpace.txt* files (Table 8).

Instantaneous speed is calculated by measuring how much the animal position changes over time. For each instant, the algorithm compares a previous position with a later position and computes the distance travelled between them. This travelled distance is then divided by the elapsed time to estimate the movement speed.

The parameter *conf.analysis.samT* controls the temporal separation used for the calculation. Larger values produce smoother speed measurements that are less sensitive to small fluctuations, while smaller values make the speed respond more quickly to rapid motion changes.

The parameter *conf.analysis.samD* defines a minimum movement threshold. Position changes smaller than this value are ignored and considered as no movement, helping reduce noise caused by small tracking fluctuations or jitter.

Table 7. *Instant_Speed.txt* content.

Time (sec)	Arena	Track	Current Speed (mm/sec)
0.0333333	1	1	65.9028
0.0666667	1	1	80.7505
0.1	1	1	76.5979
0.133333	1	1	60.8948
0.166667	1	1	67.6739

Instantaneous acceleration (*Instant_Accel.txt*)

This file shows the acceleration of the animals in each instant as second derivate of the *Tracking_RealSpace.txt* files (Table 9).

Acceleration is calculated by measuring how much the speed changes over time. For each instant, the algorithm compares a previous speed value with a later one and computes the difference between them. Larger speed changes over shorter periods produce higher acceleration values.

The parameter *analysis.samT* controls the temporal separation used for this comparison. Larger values produce smoother acceleration measurements that are less sensitive to noise, while smaller values make the acceleration respond more quickly to sudden motion changes.

Table 8. *Instant_Accel.txt* content.

Time (sec)	Arena	Track	Current Speed (mm/sec)
0.0333333	1	1	65.9028
0.0666667	1	1	80.7505
0.1	1	1	76.5979
0.1333333	1	1	60.8948
0.1666667	1	1	67.6739

Speed distribution (*Distribution_Speed.txt*)

Distribution of animal speeds. The speed distribution computes how often different movement speeds occur across all tracked animals (Table 10).

The algorithm groups speed values into intervals (bins) and counts how many speed measurements fall into each interval, generating a histogram of movement activity. The parameter *conf.analysis.dtSp* controls the size of these speed intervals. Smaller values create a more detailed distribution with finer separation between speeds, while larger values produce a smoother and more compact distribution.

Very small movements or invalid values are handled safely to avoid instability in the distribution. Additionally, if the number of intervals becomes excessively large, the algorithm automatically reduces the number of bins to keep the distribution manageable and easier to analyze.

Table 9. *Distribution_Speed.txt* content.

mm/s	Count	Rate
0.5	15944	0.596841
1	8083	0.302575
1.5	2654	0.0993487
2	25	0.000935839

Acceleration distribution (*Distribution_Accel.txt*)

The acceleration distribution computes how often different acceleration values occur across all tracked animals (Table 11).

The algorithm groups acceleration values into intervals (bins) and counts how many measurements fall into each interval, generating a histogram of movement changes.

The parameter *conf.analysis.dtSp* controls the size of these acceleration intervals. Smaller values create a more detailed distribution with finer separation between acceleration levels, while larger values produce a smoother and more compact distribution.

Invalid or unstable values are handled safely to avoid errors in the distribution. Additionally, if the number of intervals becomes excessively large, the algorithm automatically reduces the number of bins to keep the distribution manageable and easier to interpret.

Table 10. *Distribution_Accel.txt* content.

mm/s ²	Count	Rate
0.5	26224	0.984606
1	389	0.0146054
1.5	9	0.000337914
2	6	0.000225276

Transitions (*Transitions.txt*)

This function detects transitions between visible and non-visible states in the tracking data (Table 12).

A transition is generated whenever a track appears (transitions labeled as 1), disappears (transitions labeled as 0), or contains a sufficiently large temporal gap between consecutive detections (disappearance and appearance).

The parameter *conf.analysis.mnTT* defines the minimum time interval required to consider that a true transition has occurred. Small gaps shorter than this threshold are ignored, helping prevent false transitions caused by brief tracking interruptions or noise. The algorithm detects three types of transitions:

- Track appearance: If a track starts significantly after the beginning of the experiment, an appearance transition is created.
- Internal gaps: If the time difference between two consecutive detections exceeds the threshold, the algorithm registers a disappearance at the previous position and a new appearance at the later position.
- Track disappearance: If a track ends sufficiently before the end of the experiment, a disappearance transition is created.

These transitions can later be used to analyze visibility changes, entrances/exits, occlusions, or movement between regions. The time, track, position and other parameters from the first/last detection is saved in a file.

Table 11. *Transitions.txt* content.

Time (sec)	Video Seq.	Arena	Track	Pos. X (mm)	Pos. Y (mm)	Label
1.92	0	1	1	30.1997	139.79	0
16.16	0	1	2	40.3914	142.042	1
25.56	0	1	2	264.587	142.659	0
36.28	0	1	3	67.851	142.557	1
43.92	0	1	3	260.846	141.895	0
59.8	0	1	4	37.3171	142.579	1
63	0	1	4	26.5074	141.028	0
75.44	0	1	5	266.598	142.652	1
78.32	0	1	5	268.247	141.085	0
86.12	0	1	6	42.6465	142.008	1

Frozen Events (*FrozenEvents.txt*)

Frozen events are periods where the animal remains almost still for long enough.

The algorithm samples the track over time and measures how much the animal moves between sampled positions. If the accumulated movement remains below a maximum allowed distance for longer than a minimum duration, that period is considered a frozen event.

- The parameter *analysis.fmmT* defines the maximum movement allowed during a freezing event. Lower values make the detection stricter, while higher values allow small movements to still be considered freezing.
- The parameter *analysis.fTim* defines the minimum duration required for a freezing event. Short pauses below this duration are ignored.
- The parameter *analysis.samT* controls how frequently the track is sampled. Larger values make the detection smoother and less sensitive to small fluctuations, while smaller values make it more responsive to short movement changes.
- The parameter *analysis.samD* defines the minimum movement that is considered real. Smaller displacements are ignored, helping reduce the effect of tracking noise or jitter.

The following information is saved (Table 13):

Table 12. *FrozenEvents.txt* files.

Time (sec)	Video Seq.	Arena	Track	Avg. Pos. X (mm)	Avg. Pos. Y (mm)	Time Length (sec)
12.16	0	1	1	55.0868	33.9619	3.52
98.68	0	1	1	105.536	41.5467	3.6
37.12	6	1	2	188.977	74.738	7.32
51.92	6	1	2	195.399	76.9609	8.88
65.96	6	1	2	199.721	75.0917	4.6
79.32	6	1	2	208.338	75.3267	4
5.8	11	1	3	235.564	28.7672	8.24
21.16	11	1	3	223.176	27.4975	5
29.64	11	1	3	214.962	27.6328	5.8
39.08	11	1	3	202.831	27.8868	13.2

Projected trajectory (*Trajectory.jpeg*)

Images with the projected trajectories of all tracked animals, superimposed to the arena picture, and in real scale (Figure 33). The trajectory of different tracks in the same arena is colored with a different color.

Figure 33. *Trajectory.jpeg*. Trajectory projection of 5 fish in a single arena experimental setup.

Exploration (*Exploration.txt*, *Exploration.jpeg*)

The arena is divided into regular squared non overlapping zones of a size selected by the user with *analysis.zSiz*. Then, *ToxTrac* counts how many detections fall in each square of the grid, to calculate the spatial distribution of the animals in the arena.

The graphic output corresponds to colored representation of the frequency of the use of each square in the grid. To this end the matrix of the detections is normalized so the maximum frequency is represented as 1 and the minimum none zero value is coded as a close to zero constant. The color scale is linear and from low to high frequency, the color codes used go from blue to green to yellow to red as shown below (Figure 34). In the graphic outputs, the zones will be superimposed to the images of the arenas, and the zone size is represented on a true scale (Figure 35).

Additionally, the text file shows the average detections by animal in each square (Table 14), the corresponding time (Table 15), and the frequency (Table 16).

Figure 34. Color linear scale for representing the normalized the frequency of use of a zone in the heat maps.

Figure 35. *Exploration.jpeg*. Representation of the zone use (exploration) as a heat map with a grid of a size selected by the user, for a single arena experimental setup with 5 fish.

Table 13. *Exploration.txt* content. Spatial distribution of the animal positions, showing average detections by animal in each square of the arena grid.

Frame Count	25mm	50mm	75mm	100mm	125mm	150mm
25mm	0	138	47	10	12	8
50mm	9	808	282	193	148	189
75mm	0	286	114	103	96	73
100mm	0	224	126	85	63	38
125mm	13	221	122	51	61	68
150mm	0	157	114	51	65	59

Table 14. *Exploration.txt* content. Spatial distribution of the animal positions, showing average time by animal in each square of the arena grid.

Time Count (m:s)	25mm	50mm	75mm	100mm	125mm	150mm
25mm	0:00.0	0:04.6	0:01.6	0:00.3	0:00.4	0:00.3
50mm	0:00.3	0:26.9	0:09.4	0:06.4	0:04.9	0:06.3
75mm	0:00.0	0:09.5	0:03.8	0:03.4	0:03.2	0:02.4
100mm	0:00.0	0:07.5	0:04.2	0:02.8	0:02.1	0:01.3
125mm	0:00.4	0:07.4	0:04.1	0:01.7	0:02.0	0:02.3
150mm	0:00.0	0:05.2	0:03.8	0:01.7	0:02.2	0:02.0

Table 15. *Exploration.txt* content. Spatial distribution of the animal positions, showing the frequency in each square of the arena grid, (the number of detections divided by the total number of detections).

Frequency (%)	25mm	50mm	75mm	100mm	125mm	150mm
25mm	0.00%	1.54%	0.53%	0.11%	0.14%	0.09%
50mm	0.10%	9.05%	3.16%	2.16%	1.66%	2.12%
75mm	0.00%	3.20%	1.28%	1.15%	1.07%	0.82%
100mm	0.00%	2.51%	1.41%	0.95%	0.71%	0.42%
125mm	0.14%	2.48%	1.36%	0.57%	0.68%	0.76%
150mm	0.00%	1.76%	1.28%	0.57%	0.73%	0.66%

Distance to center (*Dist_CenterPos.txt, Dist_Center_Pos.jpeg*)

This output represents the distribution of the distance of the animal positions with respect to the center of the arena. Using *analysis.zSiz* to calculate the bins of the distribution for the selected size (Figure 36, Table 17).

Figure 36. *Dist_Center_Pos.jpeg*. Heatmap representing the distribution of distance to the center of the arena.

Table 16. *Dist_Center_Pos.txt*. Distribution of the distances to the center of the arena showing average detections by animal in each area, average time by animal in each area and frequency in each area (the number of detections in that area divided by the total number of detections).

Use/Dst. Center	25mm	50mm	75mm	100mm	125mm
Frame Count	190	725	1994	4270	1753
Time Count (m:s)	0:06.3	0:24.2	1:06.5	2:22.3	0:58.4
Frequency (%)	2.12%	8.11%	22.33%	47.81%	19.63%

Distance to mean position (*Dist_MeanPos.txt, Dist_Mean_Pos.jpeg*)

This output represents the distribution of the distance of the animal positions with respect to mean of the detected positions. Using *analysis.zSiz* to calculate the bins of the distribution for the selected size (Figure 37, Table 18).

Figure 37. *Dist_Mean_Pos.jpeg*. Heatmap representing the distribution of distance to mean position of the arena.

Table 17. *Dist_MeanPos.txt*, average detections by animal in each area, average time by animal in each area and frequency in each area (the number of detections in that area divided by the total number of detections).

Use/Dst. Mean	25mm	50mm	75mm	100mm	125mm
Frame Count	209	731	2059	4129	1804
Time Count (m:s)	0:07.0	0:24.4	1:08.6	2:17.6	1:00.1
Frequency (%)	2.34%	8.18%	23.05%	46.23%	20.20%

Distance to edges (*Dist_Edges.txt*, *Dist_Edge_[edge].jpeg*)

We define the walls of the arena by the lines connecting its corner points. To this end we will use a cardinal nomenclature. Therefore, the North (N) wall will be defined as the line connecting the North West (NW) and North East (NE) corners of the image and it will correspond to the upside of the arena image.

This output represents the distribution of the distance of the animal positions with respect to the edges of the arena. Using *analysis.nZon* as the number of bins so the distribution is divided into *nZon* - 1 bins of the selected size *analysis.zSiz*, representing increasing distances from the edge. All detections beyond the last zone are grouped into the final remaining bin.

ToxTrac saves text and graphic representations of these outputs as heatmaps (Figure 38, Table 19, Table 20, Table 21).

Figure 38. *Dist_Edges.jpeg*. Representation of the zone use as heat maps according to de distance to the edges.

Table 18. *Dist_Edges.txt*, average number of detections by animal in the arena.

Frame Count	25mm	50mm	75mm
Edge N	302	2660	5970
Edge W	161	2620	6150
Edge S	625	2283	6024
Edge E	26	2556	6350
Edge ALL	1074	6394	1463

Table 19. *Dist_Edges.txt*, average time spent by animal in the arena.

Time Count (m:s)	25mm	50mm	75mm
Edge N	0:10.1	1:28.7	3:19.0
Edge W	0:05.4	1:27.3	3:25.0
Edge S	0:20.8	1:16.1	3:20.8
Edge E	0:00.9	1:25.2	3:31.7
Edge ALL	0:35.8	3:33.1	0:48.8

Table 20. *Dist_Edges.txt*, frequency in each area (the number of detections in that area divided by the total number of detections).

Frequency (%)	25mm	50mm	75mm
Edge N	3.38%	29.78%	66.84%
Edge W	1.81%	29.34%	68.85%
Edge S	6.99%	25.56%	67.44%
Edge E	0.29%	28.61%	71.09%
Edge ALL	12.03%	71.59%	16.38%

Zone distance stats (Dist_Zones.txt)

Statistics describing how animals interact with user-defined zones of interest inside the arena. Different analyses are performed depending on the geometry of each zone.

For circular and polygonal zones, the analysis computes:

- Time and frequency spent inside and outside the zone (Table 22).
- Distance distributions relative to the nearest zone border (Table 22).
- Distance distributions relative to the zone center (Table 23).
- Entry and exit crossing events (Table 24).
- Zone size and occupancy statistics.

For line zones, the analysis computes:

- Signed distance distributions relative to the line, allowing differentiation between both sides of the line (Table 25).
- Directional crossing events between the positive and negative sides of the line (Table 26).

For point zones, the analysis computes:

- Distance distributions relative to the reference point (same as Table 23).

Distance statistics are grouped into configurable spatial bins, allowing the generation of spatial occupancy profiles around each zone structure.

Crossing events store the frame, time, position, and crossing direction for each detected transition. For polygon and circular zones, crossings correspond to entries and exits. For line zones, crossings correspond to directional side changes across the line.

Table 21. *Dist_Zones.txt*, frames and time per animal and frequency spent inside and outside the zone.
Distance distributions relative to the nearest zone border.

Use/Dst. Edge (bin)	Inside	25mm	50mm
Frame Count	15267	3182	7861
Time Count	508.9	106.067	262.033
Frequency	0.569792	0.118758	0.293387

Table 22. *Dist_Zones.txt*, distance distributions relative to the center of the zone, showing frames, time per animal and frequency.

Use/Dst. Center	25mm	50mm	75mm	100mm	125mm
Frame Count	253	756	2174	1992	1363
Time Count (m:s)	0:08.4	0:25.2	1:12.5	1:06.4	0:45.4
Frequency (%)	2.83%	8.47%	24.35%	22.30%	15.26%

Table 23. *Dist_Zones.txt*, entry and exit crossing events.

Crossing Events	Track	Frame	Time	PosX	PosY	Type
1	1	48	1.60	179.16	188.51	Exit
2	1	334	11.13	181.74	81.33	Enter
3	1	371	12.37	178.76	129.12	Exit
4	3	142	4.73	178.94	99.64	Exit
5	2	84	2.80	181.75	66.69	Enter
6	2	270	9.00	179.15	190.24	Exit
7	2	379	12.63	180.83	101.46	Enter
8	2	435	14.50	179.88	184.96	Exit
9	2	597	19.90	180.92	89.08	Enter
10	2	723	24.10	179.32	109.50	Exit
11	2	762	25.40	180.98	53.69	Enter
12	4	486	16.20	180.21	150.00	Enter
13	4	853	28.43	179.82	192.68	Exit

Table 24. *Dist_Zones.txt*, signed distance distributions relative to a line, showing frames, time per animal and frequency.

Use/S. Dst. Line	-75mm	-50mm	-25mm	25mm	50mm	75mm
Frame Count	1829	1178	651	702	729	1061
Time Count (m:s)	1:01.0	0:39.3	0:21.7	0:23.4	0:24.3	0:35.4
Frequency (%)	20.48%	13.19%	7.29%	7.86%	8.17%	11.88%

Table 25. *Dist_Zones.txt*, directional crossing events between the positive and negative sides of the line.

Crossing Events	Track	Frame	Time	PosX	PosY	Type
1	1	48	1.60	179.16	188.51	Neg to Pos
2	1	334	11.13	181.74	81.33	Pos to Neg
3	1	371	12.37	178.76	129.12	Neg to Pos
4	3	142	4.73	178.94	99.64	Neg to Pos
5	2	84	2.80	181.75	66.69	Pos to Neg
6	2	270	9.00	179.15	190.24	Neg to Pos
7	2	379	12.63	180.83	101.46	Pos to Neg
8	2	435	14.50	179.88	184.96	Neg to Pos
9	2	597	19.90	180.92	89.08	Pos to Neg
10	2	723	24.10	179.32	109.50	Neg to Pos
11	2	762	25.40	180.98	53.69	Pos to Neg

References

- Bishop, G., & Welch, G. (2001). An introduction to the kalman filter. *Proc of SIGGRAPH, Course*, 8(27599-23175), 41.
- Bradski, G., & Kaehler, A. (2008). *Learning OpenCV: Computer vision with the OpenCV library*. " O'Reilly Media, Inc."
- Kuhn, H. W. (1955). The Hungarian method for the assignment problem. *Naval research logistics quarterly*, 2(1-2), 83-97.
- Panadeiro, V., Rodriguez, A., Henry, J., Wlodkowic, D., & Andersson, M. (2021). A review of 28 free animal-tracking software applications: current features and limitations. *Lab Animal*, 50, 246–254. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41684-021-00811-1>
- Piccardi, M. (2004). Background subtraction techniques: a review. 2004 IEEE international conference on systems, man and cybernetics (IEEE Cat. No. 04CH37583),
- Rodriguez, A., Molares-Ulloa, A., Andersson, M., & Brodin, T. (2026a). *ToxTrac 2026*. In Universidade da Coruña. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20393895>
- Rodriguez, A., Molares-Ulloa, A., Andersson, M., & Brodin, T. (2026b). *ToxTrac 2026 User and Technical Overview Manual*. In Universidade da Coruña. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20393895>
- Rodriguez, A., Zhang, H., Klaminder, J., Andersson, P., & Andersson, M. (2017). ToxId: an algorithm to track the identity of multiple animals. *Scientific Reports*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-15104-2>
- Rodriguez, A., Zhang, H., Wilklund, K., Brodin, T., Andersson, P., & Andersson, M. (2018). ToxTrac: a fast and robust software for tracking organisms. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 9(3), 460–464. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12874>